

152nd EAAE SEMINAR

**EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES AND THE
DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE**

***P*ROCEEDINGS OF *A*BSTRACTS**

*August 30th - September 1st 2016
Novi Sad, Serbia*

Publishers:

Serbian Association
of Agricultural Economists,
Belgrade, Serbia

Faculty of Economics, Subotica,
University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Institute of Agricultural
Economics, Belgrade, Serbia

For publisher:
Miladin Ševarlić

Editors:
Danilo Tomić
Koviljko Lovre
Jonel Subić

Technical preparation and design:
Radojica Sarić & Velibor Potrebić,
Institute of Agricultural Economics, Belgrade, Serbia

Printing:
„Mala knjiga“, Zetska 15, Novi Sad

Number of copies:
300

ISBN:
978-86-6269-050-0

PRODUCTION OF HARD CHEESE FOR THE RUSSIAN MARKET

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Abstract: Given that the production of milk and dairy products in Serbia is to some extent compromised, because there is already an influx of cheap dairy products from the EU, all to the detriment of domestic producers, and it also don't benefit consumers because they do are not able buy cheaper products, it is necessary to look for other solutions. The Russian market is interesting because good prices can be achieved and large quantities of products sold. Hard cheese is particularly interesting because it is known for its quality and long shelf life. The problem of our dairies is that almost no dairy produces hard cheese for cutting and grating from cow's milk, mainly hard cheeses of pasta filata type and smaller amounts of hard cheese are made from sheep's milk.

The group of hard cheeses includes large number of varieties of cheese which are divided into extra-hard, hard with holes and hard without holes. They are characterized by: low moisture content, which is achieved by size of particles during the cutting of the cheese curd and using the high temperature processing of the curd; clean rind, or not having rind at all in the case that it is packed into some sort of foil and a method of ripening under the influence of an enzymes originating from a starter culture and rennet. This is hard cheese, that goes through a series of physical-chemical and microbiological changes during the ripening period, affecting the sensory characteristics. Below the rind is straw-coloured dough, without any cracks, which melts in the mouth. The flavour is delicate, mildly sharp, but not too narrow and complete despite a low fat content. Hard cheeses have a long ripening period, and thus have greater digestibility, higher concentration of free amino acids and a higher concentration of short and medium chain free fatty acids. The high concentration of calcium in cheese has significant impact on the formation and protection of teeth and bones, prevention of osteoporosis

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and hypertension. Thanks to its high sensory and nutritional properties, and also long shelf life, hard cheese Čarnok has a high commercial value. Čarnok cheese is mainly sold in whole sheave or cut to pieces on the spot in shops or packaged into ¼ kg pieces.

This paper describes the technological process of making hard cheese called Čarnok produced in Dana dairy plant in Vrbas. This is a new type of hard cheese in Livno cheese type that is produced in Serbia, which is already on the domestic market and will soon be exported to the Russian market.

Key words: *technological process, hard cheese, high commercial value, Russian market*